

SPACE AND TERRESTRIAL SYSTEMS
IN NAVAL COMMUNICATIONS

An address by RADM Lawrence Layman,
USN to the 21st Annual Electronics and
Aerospace Conference (EASCON 88), 10
November 1988

Good morning ladies and gentlemen.

I am pleased to have this opportunity to be with you today and to share my perspective on the place of space and terrestrial systems in naval communications.

I would first like to set our communications requirements in their operational context and then address the current and evolving systems we see fulfilling those needs. In the end, I believe you will see that we have attempted to create a balanced C3 architecture that draws upon all available media in a complementary rather than a competitive way.

As a first step in understanding the unique communications requirements for naval forces, it is important to realize their enormous operating range. Not only must we operate routinely on the ocean but under the sea, throughout the airspace above it and across the beach and into the hinterland as well. This range of operations is worldwide in scope and supporting communications must remain continuously available throughout the vagaries of the weather and unfettered by political constraints. Clearly, no single medium or generic system can adequately fulfill all our naval command and control requirements.

As demonstrated by recent world events, one of the Navy's greatest strengths is mobility. This advantage of naval forces is perhaps even more important today than at any other time in our history. The ability to conduct sustained global, forward deployed operations, whenever and however they are needed, and without the consent or cooperation of any foreign government, provides the United States a responsiveness to changing international conditions unmatched by any other country. This flexibility, however, which is a major part of our strength, places significant demands on our command and control systems. Unable and unwilling to rely entirely on major fixed sites and nodes, we are designing and fielding systems that respond quickly to changes in our missions.

The Navy's Command and Control System, the NCCS, must therefore be configured to be responsive to the entire Navy organization, both ashore and afloat. It must be equally capable of providing secure and reliable interfaces with the national command authority, other services and allied

forces. To support decision makers, the NCCS must also provide tactical, technical and readiness data as well as indications and warning, surveillance and targeting information.

The NCCS today has evolved into an interconnected system of afloat and ashore centers comprising a flexible arrangement of personnel, equipment and communications facilities using a mix of space-based and terrestrial systems. These resources are tailored by each commander to control forces in the conduct of operations for the accomplishment of his assigned mission.

These command and control systems can be divided into two general, parallel areas. Strategic programs provide assured connectivity from the national command authority to our ballistic missile submarines at sea. Tactical programs are designed to provide command and control from the fleet commanders-in-chief to and among all their assigned naval forces both at sea and ashore. Each depends upon a unique combination of both terrestrial and space-based communications systems.

In our strategic communications programs, we emphasize meeting the connectivity requirements needed to provide reliable and timely delivery of emergency action messages. Based on data collected in actual operations over the last nine years, the reliability of communications to strategic submarines has been greater than 99 percent in an unstressed environment.

The submarine radio broadcast system is a highly redundant and overlapping system of very low frequency (VLF), low frequency (LF), high frequency (HF) and UHF SATCOM transmitting sites supported by an interconnecting landline and microwave communications network. This provides a highly reliable and diverse peacetime communications broadcast and report-back system for our submarines.

The extremely low frequency (ELF) communications system provides us with a unique capability to communicate with submerged submarines. Its ability to penetrate sea water to considerable depths enhances our sea-based nuclear deterrent forces by protecting their assured survivability through reducing detectability of surface observables (magnetic, wake, and other non-acoustics), increasing communications reliability and enhancing operational flexibility. With ELF, submarines have the capability to operate continuously at optimum patrol speeds and depths while maintaining a continuous receive connectivity. ELF provides great operating flexibility to our fleet ballistic missile (FBM) submarines, thereby insuring against possible Soviet anti-submarine warfare breakthrough.

Development of the Navy's ELF system has been accomplished. The transmitting stations are complete and achieved Initial Operational Capability (IOC) in June 1986. Full Operational Capability (FOC) for the synchronously linked Michigan and Wisconsin transmitters and production ELF receivers aboard all operational submarines is expected in 1991.

The TACAMO program, which provides a continuous airborne relay capability for communications to our strategic fleet ballistic missile submarines, is a key communications node in the strategic communications network. The continuous relay capability and the added survivability provided by TACAMO aircraft increase our FBM submarines' capability to execute their mission should that eventuality ever be required. TACAMO provides obvious assurance to the Soviets that retribution for any attack cannot be avoided; it is the substantive key deterrent.

Although the turbo-prop EC-130 has performed the TACAMO mission well in the past, a replacement aircraft is required to meet mission requirements of the 1990's. As a replacement for the EC-130 TACAMO airframe, the E-6A, with greater range, payload, speed, and endurance best addresses these requirements and will allow the Navy to take full advantage of the TRIDENT weapon system's enlarged area of coverage.

The TACAMO communications system's VLF downlink to the SSBNS is being upgraded with a more reliable High Power Transmit System (HPTS) in a joint development program with the Air Force. HPTS will be installed on the E-6A and on the Air Force EC-135 Airborne Command Posts. The E-6A aircraft will also be backfitted with a Milstar EHF terminal.

While our strategic programs emphasize support for deterrence, we must still plan for an entire range of worldwide tactical operations. In the maritime area, a combination of threats drives this aspect of command and control complexity. First, the Soviet thrust to extend their naval presence to all ocean areas of the world has had a significant impact on how we must do business. Second, we live in an era of constant political flux which threatens international order and stability, particularly in the Third World.

To deal with these threats effectively and to maximize the utility of our resources, we require the capability, on a global scale, to exchange critical information and instructions with our naval forces wherever they may be and whenever the need arises. Therefore, it is important to place increased emphasis on our

tactical command and control systems to ensure that our complex and sophisticated weapons systems can respond to new threats which have increasingly shorter reaction times, lower detection thresholds, and greater mobility. Several programs are underway in the Navy to manage the timely use of data so that commanders have the survivable connectivity and information they need to employ their assigned ships, submarines, and aircraft effectively. These new command and control systems will fully support our forward battle group commanders as they contend with the threat of the 1990's, while also ensuring interoperability with our U.S. services, with NATO, and with our Allies.

The focus of the Navy Command and Control system (NCCS) is a worldwide network of 36 shore-based operational centers which provide tactical information to all levels of Navy command. The challenge facing this system is to integrate effectively a vast amount of data from a variety of sensors and to deliver this integrated information to operational commanders in a timely manner and in an easily useable format. Timely and accurate delivery of information from ashore is essential to permit the afloat commander to extend his battle horizon, in order both to meet the threat of enemy weaponry and to use his over-the-horizon (OTH) weapons effectively.

Delivery of this information and direction from our command centers is the task of the Naval Telecommunications Command. Comprised of some 11,000 military and civilian personnel located at shore communications facilities worldwide, this is the heart of our communication system and processes the equivalent of 80,000 messages per day.

This connectivity interface from ashore to our forces afloat is provided over a variety of transmission systems for fleet broadcast, teletype circuits, on-call circuits, high speed message and data systems as well as a variety of voice circuits. Near real-time imagery also is now provided afloat via the Fleet Imagery Support Terminal (FIST) using UHF satellite links.

At sea, the afloat command and control system is an aggregate of components which receives inputs both from within and outside the battle group. It accurately correlates and fuses this multi-source information for display and to support decision making by afloat commanders. This processed and correlated sensor data displays a total tactical picture and assists the commander in the formulation and dissemination of force orders and direction.

Command centers afloat are connected within the battle group by the OTC Information Exchange System (OTCIXS) and will interface with the NCCS ashore via the Tactical Data Information Exchange System (TADIIXS). These links are supported by UHF satellite communications. Clearly, as these examples illustrate, space has become an integral dimension of the battle force and must be included in the development of our warfighting strategy and tactics. The establishment of the Naval Space Command has provided a focus for the development of space systems and operations that are responsive to our warfighting requirements.

The Navy is playing a key role in this effort, and we will continue our leadership role in space. Our goal is to more thoroughly integrate current and future space systems into our warfare strategies and routine fleet operations - in essence making our space assets an integral part of the battle force.

The Navy is the largest tactical user of space-based systems and our interest, role, and dependence upon space and space-based systems continues to grow. Geographic mobility and our worldwide mission drive us to be the primary users of satellite communications, navigation, meteorology, oceanography, and surveillance systems.

The reliability of communications between both shore-based and afloat commanders and their assigned units, through our comprehensive Ultra High Frequency Satellite Communications (UHF SATCOM) System has been rewarding. UHF SATCOM systems now carry the bulk of Navy's tactical communications. However, these aging space segments must be replaced by the UHF Follow-on System in the early 1990's when the current constellation approaches the end of its expected operational lifetime. Eight satellites, plus one on-orbit spare, in geosynchronous orbit, serving four coverage areas, will provide worldwide UHF communications between 70°N and 70°S for tactical military units and specialized service for government agencies.

Demand Assigned Multiple Access (DAMA), a UHF satellite communications multiplexing system, increases the efficiency of satellite channels by transmitting a number of circuits over one channel. DAMA is operational today in the surface fleet worldwide. It provides an efficient transmission means for a variety of fleet tactical communications, including imagery, tactical intelligence, over-the-horizon targeting data, and command and control circuits. An extension of DAMA is our mini-DAMA program, which reduces the size of DAMA system components to allow installation on submarines and aircraft.

In addition to gains in satellite capacity, mini-DAMA will provide important support for our submarines by reducing time at communications depth, thereby reducing submarine vulnerability. Initial operational capability is FY 1994.

To meet the minimum essential wartime requirements in a highly stressed environment, the Navy is pressing forward in developing Extremely High Frequency Satellite Communications (EHF SATCOM) shipboard terminals. Employing the Milstar communications satellite, being developed by the Air Force as part of the joint Milstar program, these terminals will provide an anti-jam, low probability of intercept, secure, survivable wartime command and control communications system. This system will reach initial operational capability in the early 1990's and will provide a basis for needed future development of our warfighting communications.

In the area of Submarine Laser Communication (SLC), we continue to investigate the technology to employ a one-way laser downlink from space for communications to a submerged platform at depth. The Navy will maintain close coordination with the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) as they proceed in aircraft laser applications. As we look forward to future years, operating in a prudent fiscal environment, the affordability of full scale engineering developments will necessarily be limited to systems with enhanced operational effectiveness at reasonable costs.

Space systems offer an unprecedented degree of operational flexibility and capability but they are not without drawbacks. There is the concern that the space system support which battle group commanders are accustomed to in peacetime will not be available when they really need it during hostilities. This issue of "survivability" is real and concern is warranted - but progress is being made towards assuring the survival of space system support. The new space systems I have described all have been conceived and designed with survivability as a criterion.

Of course, space systems share a major vulnerability with other systems - the susceptibility of their terrestrial nodes to a variety of attacks. To counter this threat we are examining a variety of options to make both ground and space-based segments more resilient.

As I mentioned at the outset, we strive for a balanced communications system with the right mix of space and terrestrial systems to provide the capacity and robustness we require. If there is competition between the two, it

is for resources and not as alternative choices in the question of media selection.

Turning to this question of resources, you should understand that we are faced with a no-growth budget that has been outpaced by operational requirements. I do not anticipate that this situation will change.

SATCOM systems have particularly high start up costs then relatively small operating costs. Because of this profile, such programs are difficult to leverage with present year programs especially in a no growth environment. We simply don't buy space segments the way we do tactical radios. Besides the expense, they're subject to unusual perturbations as the continuing problem with the shuttle has shown. And while I'm optimistic that the shuttle will be returned to full service, I don't believe that we will ever see routine "housecall" maintenance of satellites in orbit.

Despite these constraints, we remain committed to respond to evolving fleet requirements in the modern, technology-driven wartime environment. We must and will continue to provide our operational commanders ashore and afloat with the tools necessary to monitor, direct and control the tactical situation. If you have any questions regarding our current course or future direction, I would be pleased to answer them now.

Thank You.